

THE ROLE OF THE FAMILY IN PREVENTING CONFLICTS BETWEEN ADOLESCENT

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Fundamental reforms are being carried out in Uzbekistan, especially in recent years, in all spheres of the country, that is, social, economic, political, cultural and sports. In particular, creating a healthy environment in the family, which is an important part of our society, remains one of the urgent tasks of today. In particular, the importance of this issue can be seen from the head of our state's opinion that one of the first tasks is "the need to further strengthen the foundations of the family, which is sacred to us, to create an atmosphere of peace, harmony and mutual respect in households."¹

The family is the main foundation of the society, which preserves the continuity of each nation, brings the new generation into the world and educates it as a complete and perfect person. The family serves as a place of living and a source of education for children at the same time. Also, one of the most important and sacred tasks of the family is child upbringing.

The family is a place of education and training, and the child learns moral rules, honesty, purity, hard work, humanitarianism in the family. Therefore, the family becomes the center of attention of the state, and Article 63 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "The family is the main link of society and is under the protection of society and the state."² The peace of the family, which is the main link of the society, is in turn the guarantee of the development of the state. But there are some unhappy situations between parents and children in the family, which is unfortunate because society creates a negative atmosphere in social life. Such problems mainly occur among teenagers, and the role and importance of the family is considered important.

Above, we thought about the role and importance of the family in society, and now focusing on the issues of resolving conflicts between teenagers and them will help to reveal the essence of the issue.

A number of scholars have studied the role of the family in resolving conflicts between adolescents. In particular, the Viennese psychologist Z. Freud and his students consider the unconscious aspiration as the most important basis for determining one's position, which arises as a target of some kind of initial inclination given to a person in the assessment of adolescence.

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2 Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2014. - P. 21.

This aspiration leads to the appearance of selfishness, contempt for other people, disagreement with the environment, even conflicts, unconscious needs and inclinations determine the activity of the individual. Russian psychologists Z. Emphasizing that Freud's theory is completely unfounded, they justified the fact that the teenager is characterized by a discrepancy between opportunity and demand, a tendency to show oneself and access to one's inner world.³

Working with teenagers has always been one of the most urgent problems. Analyzing the causes of this problem, first of all, we should pay attention to the identity of the persons who gave birth to the child, and secondly, to the social environment in which he was born and grew up. According to many people, problems related to teenagers have been occurring more and more recently and their number has increased dramatically. Also, this problem can be attributed to a number of external reasons, i.e. the current high flow of information (watching TV continuously, playing various games on the computer, absorbing various inappropriate information through unofficial sites on the Internet) or the attention of adults, family economy, etc.

Adolescence is a period when a person passes from childhood to youth and, in turn, differs from other periods by its relatively sharper and more complicated transition. This period corresponds to the time when children study in grades 5-8 and takes place between the ages of 11-12 and 14-15 years. In some children, this period can be observed 1-2 years earlier or later. In some special psychological literature, the period of adolescence is called "transition period", "difficult period", "crisis period".⁴

Adolescence is the period of a person's coming of age, which differs sharply from other stages of development. Because in this period of maturation, along with physical growth, the process of sexual maturation is also carried out in adolescents.

These changes that occur during adolescence affect the child's psyche and body, and during this period, the child shows negative characteristics such as capricious, stubborn, stubborn, lazy, and causes misunderstandings between teenagers. In order to prevent this, the parents in the family should teach the child how to use his free time efficiently and always supervise him, take his child into clubs taking into account his interests and abilities, teach him to use socially useful types of work productively and rationally, teachers, educators, and

parents to strengthen public control will help prevent conflicts between teenagers.

3 G'oziev E. Psychology. - T.: Teacher, 1994. -P. 136.

4 Shoumarov G'.B. Family psychology. - T.: Sharq, 2008. - P. 63.

Summing up based on the above points, we can make the following recommendations in order to prevent and eliminate negative problems among teenagers: firstly, parents should use motivational methods in relation to children; secondly, further strengthening of family, neighborhood and school cooperation; thirdly, to give him a chance to speak at various events held at the school, at various nights, among his peers, among his friends, to ensure that he is active in them; fourthly, conducting preventive measures in cooperation between family and neighborhood inspectors among teenagers with a tendency to conflict in neighborhoods.

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